

CONCLUSIONS: one of the main characteristics that determine the quality of automotive fuels is the purity of the fuel, i.e. the absence of various contaminants in it.

- the main amount of contaminants in the fuels of vehicles operating in hot climatic conditions is atmospheric dust, which causes abrasive wear of parts and failure of fuel equipment;

- with an increase in the content of quartz in natural dusts, their abrasive ability increases.

- to reduce the wear of the parts of the cylinder-piston group of automobile engines, it is necessary to properly clean the fuel and air entering the engine.

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ANALYSIS OF SCIENTIFIC APPROACHES TO THE MANAGEMENT OF THE TECHNICAL CONDITION OF MILITARY EQUIPMENT AND WAYS TO IMPROVE THEM

Baranov Yu.

Candidate of Technical Sciences (Ph.D), Associate Professor, Professor of the Department of Engineering Equipment, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy Ukraine, Lviv

Baranov A.

Candidate of Technical Sciences (Ph.D), Associate Professor, associate professor, Department of Combat (Operational) Support Units Tactics, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy Ukraine, Lviv

Kyrylchuk V.

Senior instructor, Department of Combat (Operational) Support Units Tactics, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy Ukraine, Lviv

Kovalchuk S.

Instructor, Department of Combat (Operational) Support Units Tactics, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy Ukraine, Lviv

Ivanskyi V.

Associate professor, Department of Engineering Equipment, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy Ukraine, Lviv

Abstract

The article is prepared on a topical issue related to maintaining the technical condition (TC) of military equipment (ME) in the process of its operation. The article analyzes the existing approaches to the management of TC of ME in the process of its operation, taking into account the experience of the Joint Forces Operation (JFO).

Keywords: military equipment; technical condition; maintenance; combat operations; mathematical model.

1. INTRODUCTION.

The problem of substantiation of rational parameters of maintenance and effective recovery, taking into account the structure of the object, operational factors, the negative impact of which is significantly increased under conditions of conducting combat operations (CO), is an integral part of the general problem of ensuring the reliability and maintenance of the working condition of ME, and requires the use of statistical and theoretical probabilistic methods of research to solve it [1-2].

Formulation of the problem. To date, a small number of models of prevention and recovery objects functioning process are known, that are not enough to study the maintenance and recovery of existing and, moreover, promising samples of ME, taking into account the real conditions of CO and operating factors.

There are no generalized mathematical models (MM) that describe broad classes of objects to be maintained and restored, and therefore it is not yet possible to give a clear classification of optimal prevention and recovery models.

Analysis of recent research and publications.

When searching for scientific publications in this subject area, one can not ignore the scientific works of such well-known scientists as V. Birkov [3], O. Volokh [4], P. Openko [5], M. Shaptalenko [6] O. Vorobiov [7] and other researchers who have quite deeply revealed the approaches to the management of ME TC.

The purpose of the article. Based on the analysis of the existing scientific approaches to the management of ME TC, to determine ways of their improvement.

2. RESEARCH RESULTS.

One of the first attempts to solve the problem of optimal prevention in relation to such a specific class of ME as engineering equipment has been made in the work of V. Birkov [3], in which the object of prevention is represented as one structural element, as a single entity. At the same time, it is assumed that only one type of malfunctions, related to wear or gradual change of the parameter, occurs in the object. This type of malfunctions without taking appropriate remedial actions can lead to the failure of the object. These malfunctions are detected with a probability of 1, and as a result of their elimination, the object is fully restored. Under such assumptions, the model of failure development in the object is represented by a Markov random process, according to which the object can be in three states:

S1 – the object is operable;

S2 – there is a malfunction, but the failure did not occur;

S3 – the object failed.

It is shown that the periodicity of such an object will be optimal at the maximum value of the probability of the process transition to the S2 state. Of course, with such a formulation of the problem and its solution, the obtained results are detached from practice, and poorly reflect the real processes of changing TC of the object of prevention. In addition, under conditions of conducting CO the possibility of transition from the operational state to other states (such as malfunctions and failures) should be taken into account, not only for operational reasons, but also as a result of combat damage. This significantly

complicates the prediction of the amount of ME for further recovery and, in general, the management process of ME TC.

Taking into account the object's TC is implemented in the work of O. Volokh [4], where it is proposed to use a progressive method of maintenance while serving individual ME subsystems – according to the state with the level of reliability control. Implementation of this method consists in improving techniques for determining the optimal values of periodicity of control and maintenance of ME samples while using them for their intended purpose, taking into account the TC and hourly redundancy. However, this did not consider the possibility of adjusting the frequency of carrying out preventive maintenance under conditions of conducting CO and the timeliness of ME recovery, which failed as a result of combat damage, as well as increasing the intensity of their use for its intended purpose.

The work of P. Openko [5], that is devoted to maintenance optimization of aviation equipment, provides a rationale for the methodology of predicting the durability of the anti-aircraft missile forces armament while operating according to the technical condition, which takes into account the technical condition of the objects at a certain time for further prediction of preventive measures implementation. However, this practically does not affect the efficiency of the TC control process of aviation equipment, due to the lack of scientific apparatus regarding the possibility of its timely recovery.

The work of M. Shaptalenko [6] offers techniques and models to increase the efficiency of armored weapons and equipment (AWE) recovery by predicting the volume of the repair fund and capabilities of repair and recovery bodies (RRB) for its recovery. However, these models are built for rather large-scale CO, and do not fully take into account the peculiarities of modern stabilization operations and the experience of JFO.

The work of O. Vorobiov [7] proposes methods for substantiating the rational structure and techniques of using RRB which significantly increases the efficiency of the ME recovery process. In contrast to the existing methods of "decentralized" use of forces and means of recovery, which did not take into account the significant time and resources spent on compatibility, the improved methods justify and more fully take into account the conditions for the rational use of forces and means of RRB, as well as determine the conditions under which they and the recovery system as a whole will be maximally loaded under conditions of conducting CO. However, this work does not take into account the conditions of vehicle control of individual ME samples, that is, predicting operational failures of ME, carrying out preventive works in individual systems of samples, and justifying the terms and volumes of early maintenance.

The work of V. Shuenkin [8] deals with use of queuing systems models in the process of restoring technical objects, and methods for studying the relationships between the components of logistics systems. Consideration is given to the possibility of building a recovery system with significant characteristics that do not always take into account the system's capabilities to control ME TC under conditions of conducting CO.

All this led to the need for further improvement of maintenance processes and recovery of ME, for ensuring effective management of its TC while using as intended under conditions of conducting CO.

Thus, the analysis of existing models of maintenance and recovery, as well as issues related to optimization of maintenance and recovery, showed that the scientific results obtained so far in this subject field are of great theoretical importance. At the same time, they have a number of drawbacks, which in many cases limit the possibility of their practical implementation for the study of maintenance and recovery of ME samples. On the one hand, the narrowness of many task settings, the adoption of rather rigid restrictions and assumptions leads to detachment from the practice and features of modern CO. On the other hand, attempts to bring the models closer to real processes and objects, as a rule, significantly complicate the mathematical apparatus and lead to cumbersome results that do not find wide practical application.

Therefore, there is a contradiction between the need to improve the process of management of ME TC on the basis of obtaining more adequate MM and methods for optimizing the maintenance and recovery processes, that maximally take into account the real factors and operating conditions of ME samples under conditions of conducting combat operations CO, and the possibility of practical use of the obtained theoretical results.

3. CONCLUSIONS AND PROSPECTS OF FURTHER RESEARCH.

The analysis of existing approaches to the management of ME TC in the process of its operation was carried out, taking into account the experience of JFO [1]. As a result of the analysis, a conclusion was made about the imperfection of ME TC management process under conditions of conducting combat operations CO, namely:

in the practical field – insufficient efficiency of maintenance due to the failure to take into account TC and the structure of a specific sample under conditions of conducting CO, significant non-production losses of time and resources in the RRB (units) of the tactical level and low indicators of maintenance and recovery during the performance of tasks in the operational chain;

in theory – the absence of a perfect scientific and methodological apparatus for management of TC to adjust the frequency of maintenance and determine the time reserves for the recovery of ME under conditions of conducting CO.

Analysis of the scientific results of research in this subject field showed that they do not allow to eliminate the above drawbacks, namely – do not fully take into account the specific features and factors affecting the maintenance of the working condition of ME in the process of operation under conditions of conducting CO [1-2]. Some issues related to the scientific justification of maintenance and recovery parameters require additional research. The existing MM of the process of

functioning of prevention and recovery objects do not take into account all possible conditions of ME, which leads to the disconnection from practice of the obtained results.

In addition, such an important factor as a procedure for determining the time reserve for maintenance and recovery of ME under conditions of conducting CO, to ensure the continuous functioning of the necessary number of working samples, is not taken into account.

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